
HEROES AND GENRE SEARCHES OF N. LESKOV

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Annotation.

The article is devoted to the study of one of the important issues of modern literary criticism - "Genre and style trends of Leskov's creativity".

The research is based on the analysis of the works of N.V.Leskov, revealing the chosen problem in the following aspects: in matters of poetics, at the heroic level, in comparative characteristics.

Key words.

Genre, genre scenes, the integrity of a work of art, composition, essayists of the Sixties.

In Russian literature in the 60s, there was an interest in genres, their forms and artistic embodiment. The genre image of the democratic literature of the 1860s largely determined the essay. Very often, at the same time, a separate case, a separate scene was formed into an independent work. In the article "Is it the beginning of a change?" Chernyshevsky, the critic, left a vivid description of those "leaves" and "scraps" with which one of the initiators of this literature, Nikolai Leskov, spoke.

But these "scenes", "unfinished stories", despite their seeming fragmentary nature, understatement, were distinguished by compositional coherence, completeness, genre integrity. Essayists of the Sixties are also making attempts to create large forms. Most often they go by combining separate scenes, thematically homogeneous, based on chronological sequence or elementary developed unity of place, less often – the unity of the hero.

Leskov's search for "his" genre is akin to the search of his literary associates, although Leskov himself did not realize this during these years. Not connected with the movement of the democratic diverse intelligentsia by any organizational ties, Leskov could speak out about its participants, about those whom he later recognizes as his literary associates, and from above, sharing the opinion of those

liberal democratic sympathies of the writers in whose environment he finds himself.

Nikoloy Semyonovich Leskov, like his literary colleagues, was not initially captured by a novelistic interest in personality. He very early established that preferential attention to the "whole", about which Gorky said well: "... his main thought is not about the fate of a person, but about the fate of Russia" [1]. And in search of his genre, Leskov, in fact, goes the same way that the essayists of the Sixties went to large forms. "His organic, most typical genre for him," writes B. Eichenbaum, "is a chronicle built on the principle of stringing a number of adventures and incidents on the hero ..." [4, 120].

The fairy tale is the characteristic style dominant of the democratic prose of the sixties. "From the very first pages of Sleptsov's stories and essays," writes M. Eichenbaum, "it becomes clear that they were designed by the author to read aloud and that, while creating them, he heard every word in them. No wonder he loved to perform them, as a professional actor, at various evenings and parties. Like Leskov, he was a master of the fairy tale, and therefore visual images were often pushed to the second and third plan" [6, 123].

It is impossible not to agree with Eichenbaum that Leskov is closer to Gorbunov in the manner of narration than to Turgenev.

Leskov turns to the fantastic manner very early. According to the observations of B. Eichenbaum, Leskov already in his journalistic articles on public topics is inclined to "play with vocabulary", "voice production" [6, 128].

With even greater perceptibility, the fantastic beginning was marked in his first works of fiction. Thus, in *The Robber*, the main characters are presented to the reader primarily by the measure of their "talkativeness": one of the young men who were traveling "chattered more than anyone and even bothered with his chatter", the other "knocked down more and more learned conversation", the peasant, "sitting on the box, was silent for almost the whole road and only occasionally offered irrelevant questions" [6, 128]. The "Sarcastic" story is also "sewn" from the speech fabric: in order to get information about the causes and nature of the riots in the princely estate, the narrator starts a "relative" conversation with the merchant, and he, in turn, asks "relative" questions to one of the participants in the riots.

A. L. Volynsky will also pay attention to the lack of integrity and consistency in Leskov's views, noting that "Leskov's journalistic articles, despite his extensive knowledge of everyday affairs and issues, do not make a clear and integral impression... he expresses not one, but two opinions..." [2, 18].

D. S. Likhachev, calling this feature of Leskov's poetics proper "the phenomenon of masking the moral assessment of the depicted", explains his thought with the story "Shameless". There, this phenomenon is revealed as the narrators alternate. In the story "Robbery", he subordinates the plot to himself: it is during its development that it becomes clear to the reader that the real robbery is not committed by Misha, this merchant's youngster, along with his uncle, and the "husband of blood" police chief...

The democracy of these prose writers is sometimes called "organic", "natural". I think the above is Lenin's distinction between the two types of participants in the general democratic movement provides the basis for a more precise and specific definition – spontaneous democracy. In any case, in the literature about Leskov, he has long been considered a "spontaneous democrat" [5, 18].

In the spontaneity of his democracy, one should look for the reason for Leskov's contradictory attitude to the direction of the Contemporary, and the appearance of the novel *Nowhere*, which entered the history of Russian literature as one of the first anti-nihilistic novels.

But, standing in opposition to the teachings and doctrines of his time, Leskov was not satisfied with such a position. Resisting "outside influences", he asks the disturbing question: "Whose am I?" A principled and even irreconcilable opponent of theories, trends, doctrines, he comes to the conviction that without a generalizing concept of life, its truly artistic comprehension and reflection is impossible. Neither the lessons of those spontaneous democrats who fell into copying what they saw, nor the experience of Pisemsky passed by Leskov.

The writers of that era, when, according to the popular expression, "everything turned upside down," were particularly strongly influenced by the upheaval in the spiritual and moral life of contemporaries. This was reflected in the genre searches of Russian realist writers.

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